

Organogel as Versatile Drug Delivery Technology for Phytoconstituents

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Abstract:

For the administration of tiny and macromolecules via oral, rectal, transdermal and ocular routes, organogels have shown to be one of the most efficient alternative carriers. Organogels are semi-solid systems in which an organic liquid phase is immobilised by a three-dimensional complex of self-build, interlaced low molecule mass organic gelator fibres. Phytoconstituents, bioactive compounds derived from plants, exhibit various therapeutic properties, ranging from antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects to anticancer and antimicrobial activities. However, their effective delivery to target sites remains a challenge due to issues such as poor solubility, instability, and low bioavailability. The special qualities of organogels build them a detectable candidate for improving phytoconstituent delivery. These gels can entrap and encapsulate a wide range of hydrophobic and hydrophilic phytoconstituents within their three-dimensional networks. This encapsulation protects against degradation, oxidation, and volatile loss, thus enhancing the stability and shelf life of phytoconstituents. Additionally, organogels can control the release of these bioactive compounds, allowing for sustained and controlled delivery, which is particularly advantageous for achieving prolonged therapeutic effects. Organogel represent a promising platform for enhancing the delivery of phytoconstituents. Their capacity to encapsulate, protect, and sustainably release bioactive compounds makes them valuable tools in pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and functional foods, opening new avenues for harnessing the therapeutic potential of plant-derived compounds.

Keywords: organogels, herbal products, phytoconstituents, gels, drug delivery

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

Fundamentals of organogels:

Gels may describe semi-solid systems consisting of immobilized liquid phase as a solvent that has a three-dimensional (3D) complex structure created by the gelator molecules as a result of physical and/or chemical reactions (Zeng et al. 2021). A three-dimensional (3D) complex of hydrophilic polymers called a hydrogel is able to hold a lot of water while maintaining its structural integrity due to chemical or physical cross-linking of the individual polymer chains (Vigata et al.2020). Contrarily, since organogels are primarily composed of organic continuous phases, they are less hydrated than hydrogels in this respect. Organogels are viscoelastic bi-phasic thermodynamically stable systems comprised of a gelator (any chemical capable of producing gel) and a nonpolar phase, with or without water molecules in the gelator system's network (Murdan 2005). They are less hydrated than hydrogel, in comparison. Due to their non-irritating characteristics and biocompatibility, they have become more and more significant in the administration of drugs in recent years. Even though organogel is made up of a vast number of liquid systems, it has solid-like morphological and rheological qualities (Ghasemiyeh and Mohammadi-Samani 2019).

Organogels have recently acquired interest in drug delivery due to their non-irritating qualities and biocompatibility (Vintiloiu and Leroux 2008). Organogelator's thermodynamic and kinetic stability is caused by their partial solubility in the continuous phase. Polymerization and low molecular weight (LMW) gelators are used to create organogel networks. In the polymerization process, a precursor solution of monomers with various reactive sites develops into a covalently linked network of polymeric chains. At the gel point, the polymeric network solution exhibits physical properties resembling gel (Pawar et al. 2014). Organogels of LMW gelators [MW 3000 Da] self-assemble into gels by secondary forces such hydrogen bonding or van der Waals. Non-covalently bound cluster networks that retain the organic solvent and have gel-like physical characteristics are created as a result of these pressures (Hinze et al. 1996).

Advantages of Organogels (Alsaab et al. 2016; Scartazzini and Luisi 1988; Schurtenberger et al. 1990; Capitani et al. 1996; Shchipunov 2001)

1. Template vehicle:

Organogels provide the chance to incorporate a lots of chemicals with various physicochemical properties including solubility of the molecule, molecular weight and size, chemical nature.

2. Simplicity in manufacturing:

The organogels are simple to manufacture as well as easy in handling.

3. Physical Stability:

Organogels are thermodynamically very stable system and its integrity can be sustained for maximum time frame.

4. Chemical Stability:

Due to presence of organic solvent, organogels are chemically very stable and do not promote any microbial growth.

5. Choice for topical application:

Due to well maintained hydrophilicity and lipophilicity, it promotes better penetration through skin so it is a choice for topical application.

6. Safety:

The presence of biocompatible, biodegradable and non-immunogenic excipients used in organogel makes it very safe for extended period of time.

Mechanism of organogelation:

Lecithin molecules gel when a polar solvent is present. Lecithin prefers to self-assemble into reverse spherical micelles in the presence of a nonpolar medium at a concentration of 0.01 mM (Santos and Lannes 2022). Addition of polar solvents in modest and crucial amounts, on the other hand, causes aggressive uniaxial development of spherical micelles into tubular as well as cylindrical micelle aggregates (Cordero et al. 1997). In stoichiometric ratios, the polar molecules attach to the hydrophilic heads of the lecithin molecules, forming a linear framework where two nearby lecithin molecules are connected by a polar molecule (Santos and Lannes 2022; Cordero et al. 1997; Rhee et al. 2001). This

linear shape is brought about by hydrogen interactions between polar molecules and the phosphate group of the lecithin molecules. These connections are also responsible for the one-dimensional creation of lecithin's reverse micelles. Long tubular micelles with a radius of 2.0–2.5 nm and hundreds to thousands of nanometers would form with the addition of polar solvent (Delgado-Charro et al. 1997; Gupta et al.2014). Micelles initially exist as separate structures in a solution. As they grow to a certain size, they start to overlap and intertwine, forming a 3D network. This leads to higher viscosity and viscoelasticity, transforming the system into a jelly-like structure. The stiffness of phospholipids in the phosphate group area and glycerol residue contributes to stabilizing these micellar structures. When synthetic polymers like pluronic are introduced to lecithin organogels, they create a new type of gel known as pluronic lecithin organogels (PLO gels). The detailed mechanism of organogelation is presented in **Figure 1**

Figure 1: Different steps in lecithin organogel formation

Organogelators:

Organogelators are molecules (lipidic substances) that can form gels in organic solvents, creating a three-dimensional complex to immobilize solvent within gel matrix (Kumar and Katare 2005; Esposito et al. 2018). These gels can exhibit a wide range of properties, making them useful in various applications including cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, food, and materials science. The capacity of the organogelators to form hydrogen bonds allows for the division of the compounds into two categories. Anthracene, anthraquinone, and steroid-based compounds are examples of organogelator that do not make hydrogen

bonds; on the other hand, amino acids, amide, urea, and carbohydrate are examples of organogelators that form hydrogen bonds (Plourde et al. 2005).

Polymer Organogelators:

Different polymeric structures, such as L-lysine derivative and common polymers including PEG, polycarbonates, and polyalkylene, are used as organogelators (Suzuki et al. 2007). Polymer organogelators have variable gelling capabilities through chemical structure change and can produce gelation even at low concentrations. In comparison to their low-molecular-weight counterparts, polymeric organogels often have lower gel-sol transition temperatures and greater gel strengths (Suzuki and Hanabusa 2010).

LMW organogelator

LMW organogelators, as their name suggests, are compounds like fatty acids and n-alkanes that can immobilise apolar solvents even at low concentrations (2%). Depending on the physical intermolecular interactions, the LMW organogelator produces gels with a solid fibre matrix or a fluid fibre matrix. A solid-fiber matrix is created when the temperature falls below the gelator's solubility threshold (Shchipunov 2001). To a certain extent, this is followed by the quick precipitation of gelator molecules in the organic medium, which causes aggregates to form as a result of productive intermolecular interactions (Shchipunov et al. 1999). In order to make solid-fiber matrix gels, a gelator must be dissolved in a hot solvent at concentrations between 0.1 and 15% (Shchipunov and Shumilina 1995). As the temperature drops, the attraction between the gelator and the solvent molecules decreases. Because of the intermolecular interactions, the gelator produces solid aggregates that are kept together by them. On the other hand, the system is kept stable by the remaining solvent-aggregate affinity.

Aggregates are formed in one of two ways: 1] Unidimensional fiber development with high specific (length-to-width) ratios, with lengths in the tens of nanometers and micrometers This category includes the majority of aggregates (for example, L-alanine fatty acid derivatives) (Santos and Lannes 2022). 2] Fiber growth in two dimensions (for example, hexatriacontane, which creates microplatelet configurations) (Santos and Lannes 2022). On the other hand, polar molecules are integrated into the surfactants found in organic solutions to produce the fluid-fiber matrices, which are made by realigning surfactant molecules in single or bi-layered cylindrical molecules. The cylindrical aggregates immobilise the

solvent (Shchipunov 2001). The solid and fluid-fiber matrices differ in the kinetic stability of the networks that make up the gel system. Permanent and largely crystalline networks form strong gels, whereas transient networks form weak gels (Cordero et al. 1997; Rhee et al. 2001). The nature of the networks that organogels develop determines their physical properties. Solid-matrix fibres are noted for their toughness due to their stiffness, which is due to their aggregation and alignment to form bundles (Shchipunov et al. 1999). Rheological studies have demonstrated this. In a fluid-fiber matrix, however, this aggregation does not occur (Jatav and Ramteke). Chirality at the molecular and supramolecular levels has a significant impact on the production and stability of solid fibres, although it is uncommon in fluid fibre matrixes (Shchipunov et al. 1999). Fluid-fiber matrices are translucent or opaque thermoreversible gels. They are sometimes described as "worm-like" or "polymer-like networks" because of their overall fluidity and fleeting interactions. Lecithin and sorbitan monostearate organogels are used in a variety of therapeutic applications.

Gemini Organogelators:

The term "Gemini" originates from the Latin word for twins. L-Lysine-based Gemini organogelators were invented by Suzuki et al (Suzuki et al. 2003). These organogelators were created by joining two L-Lysine derivatives together using amide bonds and alkylene spacer chains of various lengths. Notably, their bis (N- ϵ -lauroyl-L-lysine ethyl ester) oxalyl amide organogelator effectively immobilized various nonpolar solvents. Additionally, diverse oxalyl amide derivatives with alkyl ester groups (like hexyl, decyl, dodecyl, 2-ethyl-1-hexyl, and 3,5,5-trimethylhexyl) exhibited promising organogelation capabilities (Suzuki et al. 2003).

Boc-Ala(1)-Aib(2)- β -Ala(3)-OMe Organogelator:

It consists of a series of amino acid residues connected by peptide bonds, with specific functional groups that enable it to form gels in organic solvents. The "Boc" group typically represents a tert-butoxy carbonyl-protecting group for the amino terminus. "Ala" stands for alanine, "Aib" stands for alpha-aminoisobutyric acid, and " β -Ala" represents beta-alanine. "OMe" signifies a methyl ester group. This compound's molecular structure and arrangement facilitate self-build in organic solvents to form three-dimensional network that immobilizes the solvents within a gel matrix. This gelation ability makes it a potentially

useful material for various applications, including in cosmetics, pharmaceuticals, and materials science (Malik et al. 2002; Maji et al. 2003).

4-tert-Butyl-1-Aryl Cyclohexanol Derivative Organogelators:

4-tert-Butyl-1-Aryl Cyclohexanol derivative organogelators are compounds derived from the cyclohexanol structure with specific substitutions at the 4-tert-butyl and aryl positions. These compounds possess the capability to form organogels in various organic solvents. The presence of the tert-butyl group (t-Bu) at the 4-position of the cyclohexanol ring provides steric hindrance, influencing the molecules' self-assembly behavior (Sahoo et al. 2011).

Additionally, the aryl group (a hydrocarbon ring system derived from an aromatic compound) contributes to the organogelation properties by participating in non-covalent interactions like π - π stacking and van der Waals forces. These interactions lead to the formation of a gel network that immobilizes the solvent, resulting in a gel-like consistency.

These organogelators are of interest for applications in fields such as materials science, drug delivery, and controlled release due to their ability to structure organic solvents and their potential influence on the behaviour of encapsulated substances. The specific molecular structure and functional groups attached to the cyclohexanol scaffold play a crucial role in their gelation properties and potential applications (Garner et al. 1998).

General properties of the organogels:

Organogels are unique materials with a range of properties that make them valuable in various applications. The properties are highly dependent on the type of gelator molecule, the solvent used, and the environmental conditions in which they are formed and used. This versatility makes them attractive candidates for a wide range of applications across different industries. Some of the key properties of organogels include (Sahoo et al. 2011; Shchipunov and Shumilina 1996)

Gelation:

Organogels can transit from a liquid to a gel-like solid state due to formation of a three-dimensional network that induces immobilization of the solvent within the matrix.

Thermal Stability:

Many organogels exhibit good thermal stability, maintaining their gel structure over a wide temperature range without melting or losing their solid-like characteristics.

Rheological Properties:

Organogels often display interesting rheological behavior, which describes their response to mechanical stress. They can exhibit properties such as shear-thinning (decreasing viscosity with increasing shear rate) or thixotropy (reversible change in viscosity upon agitation and rest).

Mechanical Strength:

Organogels can have varying mechanical strengths, from soft and pliable to firm and rigid, based on molecular arrangement of gelators as well as interactions within gel network.

Solvent Compatibility:

Large number of organic solvents are suitable for organogel formation. The choice of solvent affects the gelation behaviour, stability, and other properties of the organogel.

Transparency/Opacity:

Depending on their structure and the solvent used, organogels can be transparent, translucent, or opaque. This property is important for applications in cosmetics and materials science.

Responsive Behaviour:

Some organogels can respond to external stimulations including temperature, light, pH and particular ions. This property has implications for applications like drug delivery or sensor development.

Structural Diversity:

The molecular structure of the gelator molecule influences the resulting gel's properties, allowing for tailoring of characteristics such as gel strength, rigidity, and elasticity.

Encapsulation and Controlled Release:

Organogels can encapsulate various substances, like drugs or nutrients, within their gel matrix. This property is exploited in controlled-release applications.

Biocompatibility:

Some organogels are biocompatible, which makes them suitable for applications in biomedicine, like drug delivery or tissue engineering.

Oxidative Stability:

Organogels can exhibit good oxidative stability, protecting encapsulated substances from degradation due to exposure to air and light.

Classification/Types of organogels:**Lecithin Organogel (LO):**

Apart from the yolk of an egg, lecithin is a phospholipid that is derived from many plant and animal tissues. Scartazzini and Luisi published the first description of the usage of lecithin for creating organogels in 1988 (Scartazzini and Luisi 1998). The primary components of the organogel matrix are lecithin surfactants as gelator molecules, a nonpolar organic solvent as the external phase, and a polar solvent like water. The formation of an organogel occurs when a minor quantity of water or other polar solvents is introduced to a lecithin solution in a non-aqueous environment. Synthetic lecithins are avoided due to their trace fatty acid content, and instead, lecithins containing unsaturated fatty acids are utilized for organogel formation. Lecithin, mainly derived from soybeans and egg yolk, is a prevalent phospholipid in biological systems. In the context of drug delivery, LO hold great promise due to their biocompatibility and amphiphilic nature, which aids in dissolving various types of drugs and enhancing permeation. LOs are stable, transparent, viscoelastic, and biocompatible gels. They consist of phospholipids, suitable organic solvents, and polar solvents, forming jelly-like structures. These gels are composed of a three-dimensional network of intertwined reverse cylindrical micelles, resembling polymers. This network immobilizes the surrounding organic phase, effectively transforming a liquid into a gel-like substance (Kumar and Katare 2005; Schurtenberger et al. 1990).

Sorbitan Monostearate Organogels:

A hydrophobic non-ionic surfactant called sorbitan monostearate, often known as Span 60, gels a number of organic solvents like hexadecane, isopropyl myristate, and a variety of vegetable oils. A hot solvent is used to dissolve or disperse the organogelator, which is then heated to 600C to create an organic solution

or dispersion that, when cooled, solidifies to form a gel (Murdan et al. 1999). When a solution or dispersion is cooled, the solvent-gelator affinities are reduced, causing the surfactant molecules to assemble into toroidal inverse vesicles at the gelation temperature. The toroids become rod-shaped tubules as a result of further cooling. The tubules join together once they have formed, creating a three-dimensional network that immobilises the solvent. Thus, an organogel develops. Opaque, thermoreversible, and long-lasting at room temperature, sorbitan monostearate gels are semisolid (Murdan et al. 1999a).

Eudragit organogels:

These organogels are mixtures of Eudragit (L or S), which contains significant amounts of Eudragit (30 or 40% w/w), and polyhydric alcohols like liquid PEG, glycerol, and propylene glycol (Das et al 2021). In order to create drug-loaded gels, the drugs were mixed with propylene glycol, the resultant solution was then added to the powdered Eudragit (held in a mortar), and the mixture was mixed for one minute with a pestle. Spreading and gel consistency are measured with a penetrometer and a spread meter, respectively. Gel viscosities increase as Eudragit concentrations rise and drop as medication content rises (Elmotasem and Awad 2020).

Pluronic Lecithin Organogel (PLO):

PLO is a specialized vehicle or delivery system used in pharmaceutical compounding to enhance the transdermal or topical absorption of drugs. It is commonly utilized for drugs that need to be absorbed by skin and reach into the blood circulation, bypassing the gastrointestinal tract.

Pluronic F127 (Poloxamer 407), isopropyl palmitate, or myristate, water, and PLO are all ingredients in this soy lecithin-based gel. Optional inclusion of sorbic acid, a preservative, is possible in both phases. This formulation presents as a yellow, odourless, and opaque gel with rapid skin absorption. Similar to lecithin organogels, PLO comprises intricate tubular reverse-micelle structures, forming temporary three-dimensional arrangements (Belgamwar et al. 2008). PLO contains a non-polar phase that makes up 22% (v/v) of it, which helps to define it as a micro-emulsion-based gel. PLO becomes viscoelastic, biocompatible, and thermostable thanks to its composition. It's noteworthy that PLO has less

risk for skin irritation. It works well as a topical and transdermal delivery mechanism for drugs that are both hydrophilic and hydrophobic (Murdan 2005).

Premium Lecithin Organogels (PrLOs):

PrLO, a distinct lecithin organogel, boasts enhanced thermostability and a non-greasy, non-tacky texture, offering pleasing cosmetic acceptance. Devoid of Pluronic derivatives, it avoids irritation on skin as well as local intolerance. Marketed as intradermal bases, PrLO premixed gels improve bioavailability by aiding bioactive agent penetration (Sahoo et al. 2011). Ideal for intradermal drug delivery, it accommodates agents like diclofenac, ibuprofen, ketoprofen, and progesterone effectively.

Gelatin-Stabilized Microemulsion-Based Organogel (MBG):

Gelatin is a protein that forms a gel when concentrated hot gelatin solution ($>40^{\circ}\text{C}$) cools ($<35^{\circ}\text{C}$). Surprisingly, when added to water-in-oil microemulsions, gelatin gels the entire solution, defying the expectation of aqueous-only gelation (Zhao et al. 2006). The resultant gel is clear. For gelatin-stabilized organogels, microemulsions are preferred due to their thermal stability and simplicity of production. An isopropyl myristate, Tween-85, and water pharmaceutical microemulsion serves as a topical/transdermal controlled administration strategy for hydrophobic medicines (Santos et al. 2008).

Limonene GP1/PG Organogel:

Limonene is chemically terpene acts as a potent skin penetration enhancer and widely used in transdermal formulations to boost bioactive agent permeation, enhancing dermal bioavailability. Limonene is effectively incorporated into dibutyl lauroyl glutamide (GP1) within biocompatible propylene glycol (PG) organogels. GP1, an amino-acid-type gelator, forms intermolecular hydrogen bonds and alkyl chain interactions, creating a solid-fiber matrix (Lim et al. 2006). Limonene-containing GP1/PG organogels, prepared at 120°C and cooled, exhibit altered rheological properties without compromising chemical stability. Terpene-based enhancers like linalool and farnesol are also successfully integrated, amplifying bioactive agent permeation rates (Kang et al. 2005).

Polyethylene Organogels:

Colorless polyethylene organogels are created by dissolving LMW polyethylene in mineral oil above 130°C, followed by rapid cooling. These organogels, functioning as ointment bases, form through physical interactions of solid fibers generated by polyethylene molecule precipitation. The resultant gelled structure finds broad application in pharmaceutical formulations (Das et al. 2021).

Fatty-Acid-Derived Sorbitan Organogels:

Hydrophobic, non-ionic gelators like sorbitan monostearate and sorbitan monopalmitate immobilize solvents like isopropyl myristate and vegetable oils, forming solid-fiber matrices upon cooling a heated gelator solution in an apolar solvent. The gel formation involves toroidal reverse micelles reorganizing into rod-shaped tubules that interact, creating a 3D network. These gels are opaque, thermoreversible, and room-temperature stable for weeks. Fatty-acid gelators form organogels through temperature-induced precipitation and self-assembly into tubular networks within water-in-oil emulsions (Upadhyay et al. 2007).

Applications of organogels in the delivery of phytoconstituents

Organogels are self-assembled molecules, such as low-molecular-weight gelators (LMWGs) or polymers, that have an organic solvent immobilised inside a three-dimensional network and resemble gels. Due to their special qualities and benefits, they have attracted a lot of interest in the field of drug delivery, especially the delivery of phytoconstituents (Qadir et al 2022). Organogels are useful in the delivery of phytoconstituents in the following ways (**Figure 2**) (Ribeiro et al. 2022; Assadpour and Jafari 2019; Tabarzad et al. 2019).

Figure 2: Applications of organogel for phytoconstituents

Improved stability and solubility:

Phytoconstituents often have limited solubility in water, which can hinder their effective delivery. Organogels can solubilize hydrophobic phytoconstituents in the organic phase, enhancing their stability and improving their bioavailability.

Controlled release:

Organogels can be designed to control the release of phytoconstituents over an extended period. By varying the gel composition and structure, release rates can be tailored to achieve sustained and controlled delivery, allowing for a prolonged therapeutic effect.

Protection of phytoconstituents:

Many phytoconstituents are sensitive to degradation, especially in harsh environments like the gastrointestinal tract. Organogels can act as protective matrices, shielding the encapsulated phytoconstituents from enzymatic degradation and pH changes, thus preserving their activity during transit.

Targeted delivery:

Organogels can be formulated to respond to specific stimuli, such as temperature, pH, or enzymes, enabling targeted delivery to specific tissues or sites within the body. This enhances the therapeutic effect while minimizing side effects.

Enhancing cellular uptake:

The unique gel structure of organogels can facilitate the cellular uptake of phytoconstituents. This can be especially useful for poorly permeable phytoconstituents that would otherwise have difficulty crossing cellular barriers.

Biocompatibility:

Organogels are typically biocompatible and biodegradable, making them suitable carriers for delivering phytoconstituents without inducing significant toxicity or immune response.

Versatility:

Organogels offer versatility in terms of formulation and application. They can be easily incorporated into various dosage forms, such as creams, gels, ointments, or injectables, depending on the intended route of administration.

Cost-effectiveness:

The preparation of organogels is relatively straightforward, and the components used are often cost-effective, making them an attractive option for drug delivery applications.

Overall, organogels provide a promising platform for the efficient delivery of phytoconstituents, offering solutions to overcome their inherent limitations and improving their therapeutic potential.

Organogel-based phytoconstituent delivery applications:

Naik *et al.*, 2023 developed polymeric organogel by combining cellulose diacetate (CA) and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), utilising phthalic anhydride (PA) as cross-linking agent. In this study, cellulose phytochemically isolated from *Dalbergia sissoo* bark biomass was used to create cellulose diacetate (CA). Over the unaltered polymeric (PVA) organogel (12%), CA crosslinking with PA resulted in enhancement of organogel stability as well as dye adsorption capacity. According to the results, organogel might be employed as a more efficient adsorbent for extracting synthetic colours from wastewater that is also

ecologically secure and thermally stable (Naik et al. 2023). Cerrón-Mercado *et al.*, 2022 formulated an organogel platform to create nanoparticles of chincho essential oil (CEO-CSNP). They employed Response Surface Methodology (RSM) alongside Box-Behnken design (BBD) methodologies to enhance the encapsulation efficiency (EE) and loading capacity (LC) of CEO. This was achieved through the incorporation of chitosan and chitosan sodium triphosphate (CS-TPP) as the matrix components. The CEO-CSNPs had a 458.5 nm diameter, an EE of 52.64%, an LC of 11.56%, a zeta potential of 23.30 mV, and a PDI of 0.418. Additionally, CEO-CSNPs demonstrated minimum inhibitory concentrations of 5.29, 10.57, and 10.57 g/mL, respectively, against *Staph. aureus*, *Salmonella infantis*, and *E. coli*. These findings may be very helpful in stabilising chincho essential oil for usage in the food sector (Cerrón-Mercado et al. 2022). Stefanov S *et al.*, 2022 studied the wound healing potential of St. John's wort (SJW) methanol extract (hyperforin-rich) loaded organogel and hydrogel in rat models. The hydrogel was developed by Poloxamer 407 25.0% and purified water 75.0 % (w/w) while organogels were formulated using borago oil 85.0 % (w/w) and Span® 60 15.0 % (w/w). The experimental group receiving organogel containing SJW extract high in hyperforin was shown to heal wounds more quickly and effectively than the control group and hydrogel-treated group (Stefanov et al. 2022). Ubani-Ukoma *et al.*, 2021 evaluated the comparative antimicrobial effectiveness of *Acalypha wilkesiana* extract-loaded topical organogel, hydrogel, and bigel. The organogel was formulated using Tween 80 and refined Palm oil while Carbopol 940 was used to manufacture hydrogel. The bigel was formulated by making the hydrogel and organogel and mixing both in equal proportions. This work documented the effective development of a topical organogel that was compatible with the two *Acalypha wilkesiana* variations. Dermoscope readings demonstrated that the formulations were safe on healthy skin that did not exhibit any signs of erythema. An effective formulation for managing topical bacterial and fungal infections was suggested by the organogel's antimicrobial test, which suggested potential therapeutic efficacy in the treatment of microbial skin infections (Ubani-Ukoma et al. 2021).

Lustosa AK *et al.*, 2020 developed topical organogel formulation of seed butter obtained from *Platonia insignis Mart* and evaluated anti-inflammatory potential. The organogel formulation was developed by using lecithin and isopropyl palmitate (1:1) with 20% poloxamer 407. In rats with carrageenan-induced paw edema, the recommended lecithin-based topical formulation was effective at all phases of the inflammatory reaction. In this study, *Platonia insignis* seed extract was suggested as a novel candidate for a topical anti-inflammatory medication (Lustosa *et al.* 2020). de Francisco *et al.*, 2020 developed organogel containing ascorbic acid (AA) obtained from propolis by-product. The organogel system's rheological and antioxidant qualities were assessed. The developed gel showed plastic flow behaviour and rheopexy. The DPPH experiment showed that organogels had an antioxidant potential with an IC₅₀ ranging from 1523.59 to 1166.97 µg/mL, respectively. The developed organogel with AA microparticles and a matrix made from a by-product of propolis is a viable delivery system for topical medications with antioxidant effects (de Francisco *et al.* 2020). Ramírez-Carrasco *et al.*, 2020 developed beeswax-based organogels using linseed oil and curcumin to improve the oxidative stability of spreadable meat products (pâté) that contained these organogels (OGCur) as fat substitutes. This study crafted linseed oil beeswax-based organogels mirroring pork backfat's properties, offering high oil binding and stability. Curcumin inclusion had no impact on structure or properties, suggesting curcumin-triglyceride interaction dominance. Curcumin notably boosted oxidative stability in organogels and pâtés, potential pork fat substitutes for omega-3-rich, healthier pâtés. Antioxidant use (curcumin) warrants attention. Organogels offer promise as animal fat replacers, enhancing pâté development (Ramírez-Carrasco *et al.* 2020). Chang CE *et al.*, 2018 studied docetaxel (DTX) and cisplatin (CIS) loaded pluronic lecithin organogels (PLOs) to improve therapeutic efficacy in ovarian cancer. In this work, an oil phase containing Capryol-90 (C90) and lecithin was developed to load DTX, which was subsequently combined into a CIS-containing PLO to create a dual-drug injectable PLO for local administration. The local co-delivery of DTX and CIS via PLOs was found to be a potentially useful platform for local anticancer drug administration with no systemic toxicity (Chang *et al.* 2018). Jose *et al.*, 2018 extensively studied different aspects of organogels through a review article. The current review article discussed some of the key characteristics of organogel, several types of organogel based on the organogelator, the manufacturing process, and many medicinal uses. Pharmaceutical companies have

investigated the potential of organogels as a flexible tool for topical and transdermal delivery applications. There are two phases in these semisolid systems: an apolar phase and a solid phase. Gels are manufactured when a polar phase is trapped inside a solid phase's three-dimensional networked structure. Solvents like isopropyl palmitate, isopropyl myristate, etc. are apolar phases. An organogelator, such as lecithin or sorbitan monostearate, is the solid phase. Therapeutic compounds that are both hydrophilic and lipophilic can be transported well by these systems (Jose and Gopalan 2018). Andonova et al., 2017 studied and evaluated carbopol hydrogel/sorbitan monostearate-almond oil-based organogel biphasic formulations (bigels) as a semi-solid vehicle for topical applications. The hydrogel was manufactured with Carbopol[®] 940 at a concentration of 1.0 % (w/w) while almond oil-loaded organogel was produced with sorbitan monostearate (Span 60, 15% w/w) as an organogelator. The bigel was prepared when heated organogel was added to the hydrogel under continuous stirring (500 rpm). The developed organogel was found to be suitable for topical application with good moisturizing ability as well as didn't show any skin toxicity (Andonova et al. 2017). Mady FM *et al.*, 2016 studied silymarin-loaded pluronic-lecithin organogels and clinically evaluated their application in atopic dermatitis treatment. The use of silymarin in drug delivery is limited due to its poor aqueous solubility and permeability which affects the percutaneous absorption. *In vitro*, silymarin permeation tests revealed that organogel (20% pluronic and 3% lecithin) was the best basis for topical silymarin administration. Redness, edema, and inflammation were all markedly reduced by the silymarin pluronic-lecithin organogel (PLO) formulation. These results supported the potential use of these unique silymarin PLO formulations as an innovative approach to treat atopic dermatitis (AD) (Mady et al. 2016). Table 1 summarises a few more organogel-mediated phytoconstituent delivery system

Table1: Application of organogel in delivery of phytoconstituents

Sr. No	Phytoconstituents	Organogelator	Outcome	Ref
1	D-limonene and nisin	peanut oil	Enhanced antimicrobial activity	Bei et al.2017
2	Rivastigmine	modified-tyrosine organogelator	Sustained delivery of cholinesterase inhibitors	Bastiat et al. 2010
3	Sinomenine	pluronic lecithin	Enhanced skin permeation and deposition	Ba et al. 2016
4	Ocimum sanctum	rice-bran wax and canola oil	Rumen protective ability	Templeman et a l. 2018
5	Eucalyptol	span 80 and tween 80	Enhanced biological properties	Singh et al. 2022
6	lupeol, curcumin, and quercetin	Myverol 18–04 k	Potential for controlled oral delivery of this nutraceutical	Rocha-Guzmán et al. 2021
7	Curcumin	lipid–Pluronic	Promising approach for topical delivery with potential pharmacological activity against <i>L. amazonensis</i>	Vigato et al. 2019
8	Clove bud oil	Beeswax	Accelerated oxidative potential	KoSFoST International Symposium and Annual Meeting 2021
9	Quercetin	Olive Oil/Pluronic	Potential carrier for topical delivery of quercetin	Elmowafy et al 2021

10	Halobetasol propionate	lecithin and pluronic	Better management of dermatological pathologies like atopic dermatitis	Lalan et al. 2017
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Applications of organogels in Nutraceuticals:

Organogels have found various applications in the field of nutraceuticals due to their unique properties and potential benefits. Organogels can encapsulate and deliver lipophilic nutraceutical compounds, such as vitamins, antioxidants, and essential fatty acids (Zetzl and Marangoni 2012). These gels enhance the solubility and stability of these compounds, leading to improved bioavailability upon consumption. Organogels can serve as carriers for nutraceutical supplements, providing controlled release and prolonged action of bioactive compounds. This is particularly useful for fat-soluble vitamins and other compounds with slow absorption rates (Lupi et al. 2013). Organogels can encapsulate flavor and aroma compounds, improving the sensory attributes of food products (Saifullah et al. 2019). This can lead to the development of novel nutraceutical-enriched culinary products. Organogels can provide a suitable environment for the delivery of prebiotic fibers or probiotic bacteria. These gels can protect probiotics during digestion and deliver them to the gut for enhanced gut health (Duraismy et al. 2022). A wide range of fat-soluble nutraceutical compounds, including β -carotene, lycopene, coenzyme Q10, DHA, EPA, conjugated linoleic acid, tannins, plant sterols, and isoflavones, can be effectively encapsulated or administered using organogels (Bhardwaj 2023). Oleogels serve as effective delivery systems for lipophilic nutraceuticals like vitamin E, carotenoids, and phytosterols. Omega-3 fatty acids, crucial for health, find incorporation into foods via oleogels, fortified with EPA and DHA from fish oils. These gels offer stability and a solid matrix, safeguarding the fatty acids during food processing and storage. Oleogels also encapsulate bone-health-promoting vitamin D, preserving its potency. Moreover, they encapsulate essential oils, preserving their antimicrobial and antioxidant properties. Oleogels prove valuable for reducing cholesterol by substituting high-cholesterol animal fats in food products, presenting a healthier alternative (Hughes et al. 2009). Table 2 summarises applications of organogels in the delivery of nutraceuticals

Table 2: Application of organogel in the delivery of Nutraceuticals

Sr. No	Nutraceutical	Oil/gelator	Outocme	Ref
1	β -carotene	Corn oil	Improved bioactivities	Fan et al. 2017
2	Lycopene	Coconut Oil	the alternative method to encapsulate various bioactive compounds	Dhulipalla et al. 2023
3	Coenzyme Q10	Fish oil	Efficient topical delivery	Zulfakar et al. 2018
4	Vitamin E	Candelilla wax	Enhancement in topical application	Martinez 2022
5	Vitamin C	Margarines Unsaturated Fatty Acids	excellent alternative to the lipid phase in margarine	Wang et al. 2021

Future scope:

The future of organogel-mediated phytoconstituent delivery is promising, with potential breakthroughs across various fields. Anticipated trends include personalized medicine through tailored organogels, nanotechnology-driven efficiency enhancements via nanogels, and the exploration of synergistic combination therapies. As our understanding of bioactive compounds expands, organogels can unlock novel applications in health and regenerative medicine. Innovative delivery routes, such as ocular or intranasal, could broaden treatment options. Moreover, organogels may revolutionize agriculture by enhancing crop growth and quality, while also contributing to eco-friendly formulations and clinical translation. Overall, organogels are poised to drive targeted and effective therapeutic interventions, underpinned by advancements in technology and delivery strategies.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, organogels have emerged as a versatile and promising platform for delivering phytoconstituents across the pharmaceutical, cosmetic, and functional food sectors. Extensive research highlights their capacity to encapsulate and release a diverse range of bioactive plant compounds. These gels effectively enhance stability, bioavailability, and controlled release, addressing challenges associated with poor solubility and absorption limitations. The interaction between organogel matrices and phytoconstituents paves the way for tailored formulation designs. Amid increasing demand for efficient and natural delivery methods, organogels stand as a frontrunner, bridging scientific innovation with practical application. Integration of nanotechnology, personalized medicine, and novel delivery routes holds transformative potential, although their realization requires multidisciplinary collaboration.

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